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COMPARATIVE PHARMACOGNOSTICAL EVALUATION OF MARKET SAMPLE OF GUDUCHYADI KWATHA WITH IT'S REFERANCE STANDARD

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Abstract

Background: The quality and efficacy of compound formulations depend largely on the quality of raw material used. Our plant-based drug industry too needs quality parameters for medicinal plants for the production of quality ensured standardized herbal drugs. Powder microscopy is a part of pharmacognosy that helps to identify and authenticate the drugs as well as impurities. *Guduchyadi Kwatha* is a reputed poly-herbal formulation of Ayurveda. **Material & Method:** *Guduchyadi Kwatha* procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India. Powder microscopy was carried out at Pharmacognosy laboratory, Upgraded department of Dravyaguna Vijnan, Government ayurved college, Vadodara. Slides of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* were prepared using the required reagent and observed under the microscope. **Observation & Result:** Powder microscopy of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* shows the presence of Starch grains, Crystal fibre, Tracheids, Vessel element, Fragments of fibres, Octahedrons crystal, Sclerenchymatous cells, Endocarp, Lignified parenchyma, Cork, Stone cell, Sclereid, Medullary ray, Aleurone grains, Reticulate parenchyma etc. **Discussion and Conclusion:** The microscopic features which were observed in the *Guduchyadi Kwatha* procured from the market revealed that it contains *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (willd.) Miers), *Dhanyaka* (*Coriandrum Sativum* Linn.), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss.), *Raktachandana* (*Pterocarpus santalinus* Roxb.) and *Padmaka* (*Prunus cerasoides* D.Don.).

Key Words:

Guduchyadi Kwatha, Powder microscopy, standardisation of herbal formulation

INTRODUCTION:

Due to the growing demand for raw materials and the scarcity of resources, many manufacturers are forced to use adulterants and substitutes, which produces inferior products. The quality of finished products varies from one pharmacy to another also there is no consistency in batch-to-batch production of herbal drugs. Therefore, it is essential to ensure the therapeutic efficacy and safety of herbal formulations and to justify their use in healthcare, standardization of these formulations.

For the present study, one of the most important herbal formulations of ayurveda, *Guduchyadi Kwatha* is selected. It consists of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (willd.) Miers), *Dhanyaka* (*Coriandrum Sativum* Linn.), *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss.), *Raktachandana* (*Pterocarpus santalinus* Roxb.) and *Padmaka* (*Prunus cerasoides* D.Don.)¹. This herbal formulation is widely used in various disease condition like, fever, burning sensation, nausea, vomiting, liver disorder etc. So, to ensure the quality and standards of the sample of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* procured from the local market of Vadodara city, Gujarat, India, along with the identification of characteristic feature of each ingredient of the combination in the sample, which enables us to identify the presence or absence of any adulterant and contaminant in the market sample.

AIM:

To study the powder microscopic features of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India.

OBJECTIVE:

1. To study the powder microscopic features of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India.
2. To compare the assessed features of the *Guduchyadi Kwatha* formulation with their standards of each of the individual ingredient mentioned in reference standard.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The sample of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* was procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India in the month of October 2024. The study was performed at Pharmacognosy Laboratory of Upgraded Department of Dravyaguna Vijnana, Government Ayurved College, Vadodara, Gujarat.

Slide preparation:

Microscopic slide was prepared from sample and saturated with various staining reagent (i.e. Safranin and Iodine) and observed under the microscope to assess their various microscopic features. Microscopic characters observed were compared with the standards mentioned in reference standard.

OBSERVATIONS & DISCUSSION:**Table No. 1: Powder Microscopic features of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* found in Market Sample**

No.	Microscopic features	<i>Guduchi</i> (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (willd.) Miers)	<i>Dhanyaka</i> (<i>Coriandrum Sativum</i> Linn.)	<i>Nimba</i> (<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss.)	<i>Raktachandana</i> (<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> Roxb.)	<i>Padmaka</i> (<i>Prunus cerasoides</i> D.Don.)
1.	Starch grains	+	-	+	+	-
2.	Crystal fibre	+	-	-	-	-
3.	Tracheids	+	-	-	+	-
4.	Vessel element	+	-	-	+	+
5.	Fragments of fibres	+	-	+	+	-
6.	Octahedrons crystal	-	+	-	-	-
7.	Sclerenchymatous cells	-	+	-	-	-
8.	Endocarp	-	+	-	-	-
9.	Lignified parenchyma	-	+	-	+	-
10.	Fragment of fiber associated with crystal	-	-	+	-	-
11.	Cork	-	-	+	-	-
12.	Stone cell	-	-	+	-	+
13.	Scleireid	-	-	+	-	-
14.	Medullary ray	-	-	+	+	-
15.	Prismatic crystals	-	-	+	+	-
16.	Crystal fibres	-	-	-	+	-
17.	Reticulate parenchyma	-	-	-	-	+
18.	Aleurone grains	-	-	-	-	+
19.	Cells of endosperm	-	-	-	-	+
20.	Microrosette crystals	-	-	-	-	+

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 2: Microscopic features in reference standard² compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Guduchi* (*Tinospora cordifolia* (willd.) Miers) Found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Guduchi</i> (<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (willd.) Miers) in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
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1.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 1.a]
2.	Crystal fibres	+	[Fig. 1.b]
3.	Tracheids	+	[Fig. 1.c]
4.	Vessel element	+	[Fig. 1.d]
5.	Fibres	+	[Fig. 1.e]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 3: Microscopic features in reference standard³ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Dhanyaka* (*Coriandrum Sativum* Linn.) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Dhanyaka</i> (<i>Coriandrum Sativum</i> Linn.) in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Octahedrons of calcium oxalate crystals	+	[Fig. 2.a]
2.	Sclerenchymatous cells	+	[Fig. 2.b]
3.	Endocarp	+	[Fig. 2.c]
4.	Lignified parenchyma	+	[Fig. 2.d]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 4: Microscopic features in reference standard⁴ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Nimba* (*Azadirachta indica* A.Juss.) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Nimba</i> (<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss.) in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Fragment of fiber associated with crystal	+	[Fig. 3.a]
2.	Cork	+	[Fig. 3.b]
3.	Stone cell	+	[Fig. 3.c]
4.	Sclereid	+	[Fig. 3.d]
5.	Fragments of fibres	+	[Fig. 3.e]
6.	Medullary ray	+	[Fig. 3.f]
7.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 3.g]
8.	Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates	+	[Fig. 3.h]
9.	Fragment of tannin	-	-

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 5: Microscopic features in reference standard⁵ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Raktachandana* (*Pterocarpus santalinus* Roxb.) found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Raktachandana</i> (<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> Roxb.)	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
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	in authentic reference		
1.	Fragment of vessels with simple and bordered pits	+	[Fig. 4.a]
2.	Fragment of fibrous tracheids containing resinous substances	+	[Fig. 4.b]
3.	Fragment of fibres	+	[Fig. 4.b]
4.	Crystal fibres	+	[Fig. 4.c]
5.	Pitted wood parenchyma	+	[Fig. 4.c]
6.	Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalate	+	[Fig. 4.d]
7.	Medullary rays with fiber	+	[Fig. 4.e]
8.	Starch grains	+	[Fig. 4.f]

- Absent, + Present

Table No. 6: Microscopic features in reference standard⁶ compared with Powder microscopic feature of *Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides D.Don.)* found in sample

No.	Characteristics of <i>Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides D.Don.)</i> in authentic reference	Features found in the sample	Figure no.
1.	Stone cell	+	[Fig. 5.a]
2.	Reticulate parenchyma	+	[Fig. 5.b]
3.	Aleurone grains	+	[Fig. 5.c]
4.	Vessels	+	[Fig. 5.d]
5.	Cells of endosperm	+	[Fig. 5.e]
6.	Microrosette crystals of Calcium oxalates	+	[Fig. 5.f]

- Absent, + Present

For this microscopic study, powder of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* which was procured from the local market of Vadodara, was selected. The powder microscopic characters of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* were observed which will be narrated further. Powder microscopy of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* shows, presence of Starch grains, Crystal fibres, Tracheids, Vessel element, and fibres suggests that it contains *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (willd.) Miers)*; presence of Octahedrons of calcium oxalate crystals, Sclerenchymatous cells, Endocarp and Lignified parenchyma suggests that it contains *Dhanyaka (Coriandrum Sativum Linn.)*; presence of Fragment of fiber associated with crystal, Cork, Stone cell, Sclereid, Fragment of fibres, Medullary rays, Starch grains and Prismatic crystals suggests that it contains *Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss.)*; presence of Fragment of vessels with simple and bordered pits, Fragment of fibrous tracheids containing resinous substances, Fragment of fibers, Crystal fibres, Parenchyma, Prismatic crystal, Medullary rays with fiber and starch grains suggest that contains *Raktachandana (Pterocarpus santalinus Roxb.)*; presence of Stone cell, Reticulate parenchyma, Aleurone grains, Vessels, Endosperm and Microrosette crystal suggest that contains *Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides D.Don.)*.

CONCLUSION:

Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (willd.) Miers), Dhanyaka (Coriandrum Sativum Linn.), Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss.), Raktachandana (Pterocarpus santalinus Roxb.) and Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides D.Don.) are included in *Guduchyadi Kwatha*.

Key identifications of features of *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (willd.) Miers), Dhanyaka (Coriandrum Sativum Linn.), Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss.), Raktachandana (Pterocarpus santalinus Roxb.) and Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides D.Don.)* as below:

Sr. no.	Plant	Key identification features
1.	<i>Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (willd.) Miers)</i>	Starch grains, Crystal fibres, Tracheids, Vessel element, and fibres
2.	<i>Dhanyaka (Coriandrum Sativum Linn.)</i>	Octahedrons of calcium oxalate crystals, Sclerenchymatous cells, Endocarp and Lignified parenchyma
3.	<i>Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss.)</i>	Cork, Stone cell, Sclereid, Fragment of fibres, Medullary rays, Starch grains and Prismatic crystals
4.	<i>Raktachandana (Pterocarpus santalinus Roxb.)</i>	Fragment of vessels with simple and bordered pits, Fragment of fibrous tracheids containing resinous substances, Crystal fibres, Parenchyma, Prismatic crystal, Medullary rays with fiber and starch grains
5.	<i>Padmaka(Prunus cerasoides D.Don.)</i>	Microrosette crystals of Calcium oxalates, Cells of endosperm, Aleurone grains, Reticulate parenchyma

The market sample of *Guduchyadi Kwatha* was procured from the local market of Vadodara, Gujarat, India, contains of *Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (willd.) Miers), Dhanyaka (Coriandrum Sativum Linn.), Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss.), Raktachandana (Pterocarpus santalinus Roxb.) and Padmaka (Prunus cerasoides D.Don.)*, all key identification characters of all ingredients are present hence it contains all the ingredients of *Guduchyadi Kwatha*.

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Plate No. 1: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Guduchyadi Kwatha – Guduchi (Tinospora cordifolia (willd.) Miers)*

Fig. 1(a). Starch grains

Fig. 1(b). Crystal fibres

Fig. 1(c). Tracheids

Fig. 1(d). Vessel

Fig. 1(e). Fibre

Plate No. 2: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Guduchyadi Kwatha – Dhanyaka (Coriandrum Sativum Linn.)*

Octahedrons of calcium oxalate crystals

Sclerenchymatous cells

Endocarp

Lignified parenchyma

Plate No. 3: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Guduchyadi Kwatha – Nimba (Azadirachta indica A.Juss.)*

Fig. 3(a). Fragment of fiber with crystal

Fig. 3(b). Cork

Fig. 3(c). Stone cell

Fig. 3(d). Sclereid

Fig. 3(e). Fragments of fibres

Fig. 3(f). Aleurone grains ray

Fig. 3(g). Starch grains

Fig. 3(h). Prismatic crystals of Calcium oxalates

Plate No. 4: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Guduchyadi Kwatha – Raktachandana (Pterocarpus santalinus Roxb.)*

Fig. 4(a). Fragment of vessels

Fig. 4(b). Reticulate parenchyma

Fig. 4(c). Fragment of fibers

Fig. 4(d). Crystal

Fig. 4(e). Pitted wood parenchyma

Fig. 4(f). Prismatic crystals

Fig. 4(g). Medullary rays

Fig. 4(h). Starch grains

Plate No. 5: Photos of Powder Microscopy of *Guduchyadi Kwatha – Padmaka*

(*Prunus cerasoides* D.Don.)

Fig. 5 (a). Stone

Fig. 5(b). Tracheids containing resinous substances

Fig. 5(c). Fragment of fibers

Fig. 5 (d). Vessel's

Fig. 5(e). Pitted wood parenchyma

Fig. 5(f). Prismatic

REFERENCES:

1. Shri Vaidhyanatha, Ayurveda Sarasangraha, Shri Vaidhyanatha ayurveda bhavana limited, Ilahabad, 2015, Kwatha prakarana, p.803
2. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Tinospora cordifolia* (Willd.) Miers ex Hook. F. & Thoms., Vol 1, ICMR, New Delhi, 2003, p. 212.
3. The Ayurvedic pharmacopoeia of India, Part -2, Vol.-1, First edition, 2008, Avaleha Kalpana, Bilvadileha, Dhanyaka

4. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss., Vol 8, ICMR, New Delhi, 2003, p. 77.
5. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Pterocarpus marsupium* Roxb., Vol 6, ICMR, New Delhi, 2003, p. 205.
6. A.K. Gupta et al., Quality Standards of Indian Medicinal Plants, *Prunus cerasoides* D. Don., Vol 7, ICMR, New Delhi, 2003, p. 227.

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